

MOISTURE EXPANSION OF GRAPHITE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In order to elucidate moisture distortion of graphite composites, moisture weight gains (MWG) and coefficients of moisture expansion (CME) of graphite fiber reinforced epoxy or PEEK composites were studied. The CMEs of unidirectional and multidirectional laminates were measured in both longitudinal and transverse directions. An application of graphite composites to optical structures will be discussed from these data.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Graphite/Epoxy; Graphite/PEEK; Moisture expansion; Moisture weight gain

1. INTRODUCTION

Graphite composites have been applied to spacecraft structures. The applications have extended to dimensionally critical structures and instruments such as telescope housings, mirrors, antennas and so on. One of the important factors to dimensional stability is moisture expansion, as well as, thermal distortion. It has been discussed in reports [1]-[7]. The moisture distortion must be considered in design, selection of materials and environmental conditions of fabrication and storage. During fabrication and storage of products, moisture is gradually absorbed. On the other

hand, it is desorbed in the space. In both processes, the dimensional change of composite occurs.

Moisture distortion of composites should be limited up to 10×10^{-6} m/m for optical use because it causes a change of a focus in an optical system. To achieve this requirement, it's necessary to evaluate materials, moisture protect measures and suitable orientation of fiber directions. The MWG and CMEs of graphite composites were tested. The results are presented in this paper.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials and specimens Description of specimens and properties of each resin and carbon fiber used in the tests are shown in Table 1 and 2. Two kinds of epoxy resins and PEEK (Vicatex[®]) were compared. K13A[®], M60J[®] and AS4[®] are ultra high, high and low modulus fibers. They were untwisted. A sealing effect of aluminum foil against moisture was also evaluated. Besides unidirectional laminates, ($\pm 15^\circ/\pm 75^\circ/\pm 15^\circ$) laminates, which can be applied to a structural rod, were tested and compared with the results of calculation.

Shapes of specimens are shown in Fig.1 and 2. Specimens uncovered with aluminum foil were put aluminum adhesive tape around (or two sides) edges to limit moisture absorption through exterior surfaces.

TABLE 1 Description of specimens: $V_f = 55 - 60\%$

No.	fiber	resin	layup	seal	test (specimen)	
					MWG	CME
1	—	Epoxy A	—	—	○(Fig.1-a)	—
2	—	Epoxy B	—	—	○(/)	—
3	K13A	Epoxy A	0°	—	○(/)	○(Fig.2-a)
4	/	Epoxy B	/	—	○(/)	○(/)
5	M60J	Epoxy A	/	—	○(/)	○(/)
6	/	Epoxy B	/	—	○(/)	○(/)
7	AS4	PEEK	/	—	○(/)	○(/)
8	K13A	Epoxy A	/	Al foil	○(Fig.1-b)	○(Fig.2-b)
9	M60J	/	/	/	○(/)	○(/)
10	/	/	(case I) $\pm 15^\circ/\pm 75^\circ/\pm 15^\circ$ =11/3/11	—	—	○(Fig.2-a)
11	/	/	(case II) $\pm 15^\circ/\pm 75^\circ/\pm 15^\circ$ =48.5/3/48.5	—	—	○(/)

TABLE 2 Properties of resin and fiber

property	unit	resin			fiber		
		Epoxy A*	Epoxy B**	PEEK (Victrex)	K13A	M60J	AS4
tensile modulus E	GPa	2.79	2.84	3.63	785	588	230
tensile strength σ	MPa	—	54	92	2840	3820	3580
density ρ	$\times 10^{-3} \text{kg/m}^3$	1.19	1.14	1.32	2.15	1.94	1.78
glass transition point Tg	K	426	473	413	—	—	—
thermal expansion coefficient α	$\times 10^{-6} \text{K}^{-1}$	80	—	47	< 0	< 0	< 0

*Aromatic amine cured epoxy resin

**Amine cured acrylic modified epoxy resin

FIGURE 1. Geometry of the moisture weight gain test specimen
() : neat resin specimen

FIGURE 2. Geometry of the coefficient of moisture expansion test specimen

2.2 Methods The temperature and relative humidity (R.H.) were 333K and 55%R.H. respectively. Before tests, each specimens were dried out at 373K for 40 hours.

2.2.1 MWG Both before and after the test, the weight of a specimen was measured.

2.2.2 CME Schematic views of the tests are shown in Fig.3. A chamber has a double quartz glass wall. Water at a constant temperature circulates through it, so that the temperature in the chamber is kept constant. A specimen is put on a quartz glass bench. Dimensional change is detected by a quartz glass rod. Movement is changed into electric signals by a differential transformer. Data were taken every 30 seconds for 24 hours. The procedure of measurement is shown in Fig.4. Both before and after the test, the weight of a specimen was measured and CME was calculated from length change and weight gain (equation 1).

FIGURE 3. Schematic views of the CME test

FIGURE 4. Procedure of the CME test

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 MWG The weight changes of two types of epoxy resins and epoxy matrix composites are shown in Fig. 5. Properties of PEEK and a PEEK matrix composite are shown in the same Figures. This indicates that MWG of aromatic amine cured epoxy resin was smaller than that of amine cured acrylic modified epoxy resin. On the other hand, PEEK absorbs moisture a half less than epoxy. Taking into account fiber's density, there wasn't much difference among composites with different modulus fibers.

The moisture protect effect of aluminum foil has been reported [1],[2] Aluminum foil used in this test reduced moisture absorption to 20 or 30 percent of bare composites. If pinholes could be reduced, aluminum foil would be more effective.

FIGURE 5. MWG at 333K and 55%R.H.
 *,** ICI catalog

3.2 CME The results of CME of various composites are shown in Fig.6 and 7. Typical longitudinal and transverse moisture distortions of unidirectional laminates are presented in Fig. 8 to 10 and typical longitudinal and transverse moisture distortions of angle ply laminates are presented in Fig. 11 and 12.

Transverse CMEs of unidirectional epoxy resin matrix laminates were approximately the same. On the other hand, the transverse CME of PEEK matrix laminates was a half or one third of that of epoxy resin matrix laminates. Longitudinal CMEs of unidirectional composites were a little unstable. It can't be specified whether this behavior was due to samples or the test instrument.

Aluminum foil didn't affect CME.

The longitudinal CMEs of angle ply laminates resulted in negative values. Calculated values by laminate theory are shown in Fig.7. β_{11} and β_{22} are measured CME of unidirectional laminates (M60J / epoxy A). Longitudinal CMEs coincide with the measured data.

FIGURE 6. CME of unidirectional laminate at 333K and 55%R.H.

FIGURE 7. CME of multidirectional laminate at 333K and 55%R.H.
 x: calculated value

$$\begin{bmatrix} \beta_{11} = -0.98 \times 10^{-4} \times 10^{-3} \text{wt}\%^{-1} \\ \beta_{22} = 0.30 \times 10^{-2} \times 10^{-3} \text{wt}\%^{-1} \end{bmatrix}$$

3.3 Moisture distortion (discussion)

$$\text{moisture distortion [m/m]} = \Delta L/L = \text{CME} \times \Delta W \quad \dots (2)$$

Taking into account manufacturing properties, high strength fiber M60J / aromatic amine cured epoxy resin is practical. Assuming that a product absorbs moisture during fabrication and storage of 6 months and dries out completely in the space, how much distortion will occur? If it doesn't have any moisture barriers, it will absorb 0.3 - 0.5 wt% moisture. In a layup of $(\pm 15^\circ / \pm 75^\circ / \pm 15^\circ) = (11/3/11)$, distortion after launch is about $-30 - 50 \times 10^{-6}$ m/m. If it's covered with aluminum foil, the moisture content will be 0.05 - 0.1 wt%. Therefore, distortion is reduced to $-5 - 10 \times 10^{-6}$ m/m. If the length

FIGURE 8. Typical longitudinal moisture deformation of unidirectional laminate (1) [M60J/Epoxy A]

FIGURE 9. Typical longitudinal moisture deformation of unidirectional laminate (2) [AS4/PEEK]

FIGURE 10. Typical transverse moisture deformation of unidirectional laminate [M60J/Epoxy A]

FIGURE 11. Typical longitudinal moisture deformation of multi-directional laminate [M60J/Epoxy A] ($\pm 15^\circ \pm 75^\circ \pm 15^\circ$) = (11/3/11)

FIGURE 12. Typical transverse moisture deformation of multi-directional laminate [M60J/Epoxy A] ($\pm 15^\circ \pm 75^\circ \pm 15^\circ$) = (11/3/11)

of a rod is 500mm, it will change 2.5 or 5 μm . Smaller expansion can be attained by more suitable orientation of the laminate plies. Though PEEK is used as a matrix resin, it will be difficult to meet the criteria of dimensional stabilities without any moisture barriers. However, PEEK may be effective to a pseudoisotropic plane that is more affected by matrix properties.

4. CONCLUSION

1. Moisture weight gain of aromatic amine cured epoxy resin is smaller than that of amine cured acrylic modified epoxy.
2. Graphite composites covered with aluminum foil moisture absorbs one third to one fifth the amount of moisture as uncovered composites.
3. M60J / aromatic amine cured epoxy resin composites covered with aluminum foil can meet the moisture requirement, less than 10×10^{-6} m/m.
4. The transverse CME of PEEK matrix laminates is a half or one third of that of epoxy resin matrix laminates.

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